

Hansch Analysis for Some Antineoplastic Glutarimides

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Hansch analysis has been performed for 38 glutarimide analogs with the help of an IBM 1130 computer. Results of computation reveal that the partition coefficients of these compounds alone can not explain their observed biological activities. This, however, indirectly suggests that the electronic and steric parameters need be considered for explaining their biological activities.

EARLIER, details of synthesis and procedure for biological evaluation of some glutarimide analogs of the type (I) in Ehrlich ascites carcinoma have been reported from this laboratory^{1,2}, the cell count and tumour weight inhibition being regarded as the activity parameters. This article covers the results of computation carried on these compounds as per the Hansch formalism³⁻⁶. Partition coefficients required for these compounds have

not been experimentally determined by the authors, but have been computed from the available literature^{5,7,8} in accordance with the standard procedures.

The main objective in this work has been to find out the extent of dependence of biological activities of these compounds on their hydrophobicity constants. As such the following equation (1) has been utilized for this purpose :

$$Y = K_1 \Sigma \pi + K_2 \Sigma \pi^2 + K_3 \quad \dots (1)$$

where, Y = Biological activity; π = Hydrophobicity constant.

Based on this, 38 simultaneous equations of the type (1) representing 38 compounds are constructed. Matrix representation of this set of equations along with their hydrophobicity constants and logarithm of their biological activities is recorded in Table 1.

Least square solution of this set of simultaneous equations with the help of an IBM 1130 computer gives the following two best fitting equations (2 and 3) :

$$\log \text{Percent cell inhibition} = 0.0258 \Sigma \pi - 0.00384 \Sigma \pi^2 + 1.772 \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\log \text{Tumor weight inhibition} = 0.0465 \Sigma \pi - 0.00399 \Sigma \pi^2 + 1.75 \quad \dots (3)$$

Calculated activities of these compounds along with the standard deviations (S) and multiple correlation coefficients (R) are also recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MATRIX REPRESENTATION OF THE GLUTARIMIDES (I) WITH STANDARD DEVIATIONS (S) AND MULTIPLE CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS (R)

Sl. No.	Compound Type			$\Sigma \pi$	$\Sigma \pi^2$	Run (1) Log Percent Cell Inhibition		Run (2) Log Tumor Weight Inhibition	
	R_1	R_2	R_3			Obs.	Calcd.	Obs.	Calcd.
1.	H	H	H	-0.76	0.58	1.625	1.749	1.221	1.713
2.	H	Phenyl	H	1.37	1.88	1.990	1.799	1.934	1.807
3.	H	Phenyl	CH ₃	1.87	3.50	1.979	1.806	1.937	1.823
4.	H	Phenyl	C ₂ H ₅	2.37	5.62	1.971	1.811	1.913	1.838
5.	H	Phenyl	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	2.87	8.24	1.986	1.814	1.992	1.851

TABLE 1 (Contd.)

Sl. No.	Compound Type			$\Sigma\pi$	$\Sigma\pi^2$	Run (1) Log Percent Cell Inhibition		Run (2) Log Tumor Weight Inhibition	
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃			Obs.	Calcd.	Obs.	Calcd.
6.	H	Phenyl	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	3.37	11.36	1.982	1.815	1.994	1.862
7.	H	Phenyl	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	3.87	14.98	1.923	1.814	1.853	1.871
8.	H	Phenyl	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	4.37	19.10	1.789	1.811	1.853	1.877
9.	H	Phenyl	Phenyl	3.50	12.25	1.956	1.814	1.154	1.864
10.	H	Phenyl	Benzyl	3.62	13.10	2.000	1.814	1.906	1.866
11.	H	Phenyl	Cyclohexyl	3.83	14.67	1.932	1.814	1.906	1.870
12.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	H	1.35	1.82	1.523	1.799	1.477	1.806
13.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	CH ₃	1.85	3.42	1.652	1.806	1.778	1.823
14.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₂ H ₅	2.35	5.52	1.799	1.811	1.988	1.838
15.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	2.85	8.12	2.000	1.814	2.000	1.851
16.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	3.35	11.22	1.454	1.815	1.965	1.861
17.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	3.85	14.82	1.883	1.814	1.965	1.870
18.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	4.35	18.92	1.799	1.811	1.962	1.877
19.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Phenyl	3.48	12.11	1.881	1.814	1.924	1.864
20.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Benzyl	3.60	12.96	1.822	1.814	1.948	1.866
21.	H	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Cyclohexyl	3.81	14.52	1.429	1.814	1.769	1.870
22.	Phthalimido	H	H	0.39	0.15	1.655	1.781	1.778	1.768
23.	Phthalimido	H	CH ₃	0.89	0.79	1.968	1.791	1.574	1.789
24.	Phthalimido	H	C ₂ H ₅	1.39	1.93	1.997	1.800	1.699	1.807
25.	Phthalimido	H	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	1.89	3.57	1.939	1.806	1.829	1.824
26.	Phthalimido	H	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	2.39	5.71	1.816	1.811	1.875	1.839
27.	Phthalimido	H	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	2.89	8.35	1.435	1.814	1.648	1.851
28.	Phthalimido	H	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	3.39	11.49	1.992	1.815	1.978	1.862
29.	Phthalimido	H	Phenyl	2.52	6.35	1.941	1.812	1.993	1.842
30.	Phthalimido	H	Benzyl	2.64	6.97	2.000	1.813	1.924	1.845
31.	Phthalimido	H	Cyclohexyl	2.85	8.12	1.677	1.814	1.638	1.851
32.	4-Nitrophthalimido	H	H	0.11	0.01	1.986	1.774	1.970	1.755
33.	3-Nitrophthalimido	H	H	0.11	0.01	1.985	1.774	1.963	1.755
34.	3-Nitrophthalimido	H	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	3.11	9.67	1.196	1.814	1.806	1.856
35.	<i>o</i> -Sulfobenzoicimido	H	H	0.15	0.0225	0.749	1.775	1.533	1.757
36.	Benzenesulfonamido	H	H	-0.45	0.2	2.000	1.759	2.000	1.729
37.	<i>p</i> -Toluenesulfonamido	H	H	0.06	0.0036	1.926	1.773	1.946	1.753
38.	<i>p</i> -Acetamidobenzene-sulfonamido.	H	H	-2.30	5.29	1.758	1.692	1.686	1.622

For run (1): $S = 0.262877$; $R = 0.0069$. For run (2): $S = 0.19658$; $R = 0.0733$.

Conclusion

The insignificant values of the coefficients of π and those of multiple correlation coefficients (R) clearly indicate that the biological activities of these compounds can not be explained by the parameter π alone. Other parameters like electronic (σ) and steric (E_s) need be brought into computation for explaining the activities.

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